

SENTENCE STRUCTURE AND RHETORICAL STRATEGIES OF HEADLINES IN NEWS REPORTS

Xayrullayeva Xonzoda Tolibjon qizi

Uzbek state world languages university,

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

E-mail: xonzodaxayrullayeva1218@gmail.com

Abstract. This article examines the headline studies in The New York Times and Xalq so'zi, applying Mann and Thompson's nucleus-satellite model along with Simpson's stylistic approach. It sheds light on how rhetorical decisions affect the meanings, emphasis and perception of an audience. The analysis indicates that The New York Times employs a blend of simple, complex, and compound sentence constructions within their headlines. Such choices augment clarity, contrast, emphasis, and emotional appeal through evocative language and evaluative adjectives. In comparison to The New York Times, Xalq so'zi headlines predominantly utilize simple declarative sentences with neutral phrases. The key focal point is placed at the tail end of the sentence, surrounded by a bland tone and a lack of stylistic flourishes. The study demonstrates a tendency within English-language news to prioritize impact and immediacy, while experiencing under formal structure and context in Uzbek news. This highlighting of contrast reveals the broader cultural and journalistic norms that define distinct rhetorical strategies across language and national media boundaries. The article contributes to comprehend how language shapes the public discourse and interpretation of the news.

Key words: news reports, articles, headlines, rhetoric, sentence structure, media discourse, stylistic analysis, sentence structure

Rhetoric is the art of using language effectively to persuade an audience. It relies on various linguistic techniques to shape beliefs, influence opinions, and appeal to emotions (Baker & Ellence, 2011). At its core, rhetoric is both the craft of producing texts and the strategic use of language to persuade, where every word choice serves a specific function based on the intended audience (Fahnestock, 2005). Historically, rhetoric has always been about analyzing and understanding the effects of language-how particular words, structures, and styles can make speech or writing more persuasive and engaging (Giovanelli & Mason, 2018). The study of rhetoric dates back to Aristotle, who viewed it as an essential part of philosophical debate (Bradford, 1997). As Harris(2018) explains, the philosophy of rhetoric can be summed up in three key ideas: *1)the purpose of writing it to communicate; 2)interesting writing is more likely to be read than boring writing; 3)skillful rhetoric is a friend, not a foe, of clarity and effectiveness.* This theory was re-written and cited by Hassan in 2024. Hassan made an contrastive analysis that was carried out on data selected from the British broadsheet The Guardian and the American New York Times newspaper headlines. He analyzed 10 political headlines from each

newspaper according to Mann and Thompson’s model of rhetoric and stylistic analysis. This model focuses on *nucleus* (main idea) and *satellite* (supporting information) frameworks. It helps to identify how headlines structure meaning, and emphasizing what is the most important. Moreover, Mann and Thompson’s model employed to analyze sentence relations, showing how various parts contribute to persuasion. Besides Hassan wrote about a stylistic analysis by Simpson (2004). It examines sentence types like simple, complex and compound, identifies foregrounding techniques, such as parallelism and deviation, which make headlines stand out. Simpson’s model analyzes also adverbs and adjectives to reveal implicit bias and tone in reporting news.

Headlines selected from The New York Times

№	Examples
1	Power, Money, Territory: how Trump Shook the World in 50days
2	What Elon Musk’s Suit Says about Trump and Power
3.	Putin Stops Far Short of Agreeing to a Cease-Fire, but Says He is Opoen to One
4.	In Europe Adrift, Macron Seizes the Moment
5.	Israel-Hamas Talks Deadlocked as Trump Envoy Turns to Ukraine
6.	Khalil Sues Columbia and Lawmakers to keep Activists’ Names Secret
7.	What We’ve Learned About School Closures for the Next Pandemic
8.	Russia Claims to have Regained Control of Key Kursk Town
9.	Teenagers Say Girls Are Equal to Boys inSchool, or Are Ahead
10.	China Cools on Musk:”Two Cars for the Price of One Tesla”

Headlines from New York Times are analyzed using Mann and Thompson’s model, distinguishing between nucleus and satellite elements. This classification determines which parts of the sentence carry the core message and which serve a supporting role. For instance, in *Power, Money, Territory: How Trump Shook the World in 50days*, the nucleus is *How Trump shook the World in 50 days*, while *Power, Money, Territory* acts as satellite providing thematic framing. Headlines such a *Russia Claims to Have Regained Control of Key Kursk Town* present a straightforward n-s structure, where *Russia Claims* functions as the nucleus, while *to Have Regained Control of Key Kursk Town* serves as the supporting detail. Compound structures, like *Putin Stops Far Short of Agreeing to a Cease-fire, but says He Is Open to One*, distribute the nucleus across the two independent clauses: *Putin Stops Far Short of Agreeing to a Cease-fire* and *But Says He Is Open to One*, maintaining an implicit contrast between the two. The distribution of N-S elements in The New York Times headlines suggests a focus on presenting information in a layered manner, allowing for contrast, emphasis, or suspense.

Headlines selected from Xalq so'zi

№	Examples
1.	Senat qo'mitasida qonunchilikka kiritilayotgan o'zgartirish va qo'shimchalar muhokama qilindi.
2.	Uzoq kutilgan kelishuv: Putin urushni to'xtatishga rozi bo'ldi.
3.	O'zbekiston Prezidentining Fransiyaga davlat tashrifi yakunlandi
4.	Chiqindilarni belgilanmagan joylarga tashlaganlarga qarshi reytd boshlandi
5.	Senat qo'mitasida zargarlik sanoati, yo'l harakati xavfsizligi va Milliy gvardiyaga oid qonunlar muhokama qilindi
6.	O'zbekiston va Fransiyaga munosabatlarini strategik sheriklik darajasiga ko'targan tarixiy tashrif
7.	Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlariga tegishli Prezident farmoni e'lon qilindi.
8.	Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti QS reytingida TOP-500 talikdan joy oldi
9.	O'zbekiston milliy metrologiya institutining rivojlanish yo'lidagi qadamlari
10.	Shifokorlar va olimlar AQSHda Donald Tramp siyosatiga qarshi norozilik bildirishdi

Similarly, Xalq so'zi headlines are examined through the same rhetorical framework. In *Senat qo'mitasida qonunchilikka kiritilayotgan o'zgartirish va qo'shimchalar muhokama qilindi*, the nucleus is *muhokama qilindi* (was discussed), while the rest of the headline functions as a satellite detailing the subject of the discussion. The headline *Uzoq kutilgan kelishuv: Putin urushni to'xtatishga rozi bo'ldi* follows a similar pattern, where *Putin urushni to'xtatishga rozi bo'ldi* (Putin agreed to stop the war) is the nucleus, and *uzoq kutilgan kelishuv* (long-awaited agreement) provides context. A headline such as *Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti QS reytingida TOP-500 talikdan joy oldi* is structured with the nucleus in *joy oldi* (secured a place), while the satellite provides the specifics of the ranking. Unlike the New York Times, Xalq so'zi headlines tend to present the primary information toward the end of the sentence, reflecting a structural preference for context before assertion.

№	Headline	Sentence type
1	Power, Money, Territory: how Trump Shook the World in 50days	Complex
2	What Elon Musk's Suit Says about Trump and Power	Simple
3.	Putin Stops Far Short of Agreeing to a Cease-Fire, but Says He is Opoen to One	Compound
4.	In Europe Adrift, Macron Seizes the Moment	Simple
5.	Israel-Hamas Talks Deadlocked as Trump Envoy Turns to Ukraine	Complex
6.	Khalil Sues Columbia and Lawmakers to keep Activists' Names Secret	Simple

7.	What We've Learned About School Closures for the Next Pandemic	Simple
8.	Russia Claims to have Regained Control of Key Kursk Town	Simple
9.	Teenagers Say Girls Are Equal to Boys in School, or Are Ahead	Compound
10.	China Cools on Musk: "Two Cars for the Price of One Tesla"	Simple

Using Simpson's (2004) framework, The New York Times headlines presents a mix of sentence types and stylistic features. The prevalence of simple sentences (e.g., *Russia Claims to Have Regained Control of Key Kursk Town*) highlights directness. Compound sentences (e.g., *Putin Stops Far Short of Agreeing to a Cease-fire, but Says He Is Open To One*) allow for contrast and emphasis. Adverbs such as *far short* and *direct* challenge intensify the headlines, while adjectives like *key* in *Key Kursk Town* signal importance.

No	Headlines	Sentence type
1.	Senat qo'mitasida qonunchilikka kiritilayotgan o'zgartirish va qo'shimchalar muhokama qilindi.	Simple
2.	Uzoq kutilgan kelishuv: Putin urushni to'xtatishga rozi bo'ldi.	Complex
3.	O'zbekiston Prezidentining Fransiyaga davlat tashrifi yakunlandi	Simple
4.	Chiqindilarni belgilanmagan joylarga tashlaganlarga qarshi reytd boshlandi	Simple
5.	Senat qo'mitasida zargarlik sanoati, yo'l harakati xavfsizligi va Milliy gvardiyaga oid qonunlar muhokama qilindi	Compound
6.	O'zbekiston va Fransiyaga munosabatlarini strategik sheriklik darajasiga ko'targan tarixiy tashrif	Simple
7.	Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlariga tegishli Prezident farmoni e'lon qilindi.	Simple
8.	Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti QS reytingida TOP-500 talikdan joy oldi	Simple
9.	O'zbekiston milliy metrologiya institutining rivojlanish yo'lidagi qadamlari	Simple
10.	Shifokorlar va olimlar AQSHda Donald Tramp siyosatiga qarshi norozilik bildirishdi	Compound

Simple declarative structures dominate (e.g., *O'zbekiston Prezidentining Fransiyaga davlat tashrifi yakunlandi*). Compound sentences (e.g., *Senat qo'mitasida zargarlik sanoati, yo'l harakati xavfsizligi va Milliy gvardiyaga oid qonunlar muhokama qilindi*) accommodate multiple themes. Stylistically, Xalq

so'zi headlines are neutral, with minimal use of evaluative adjectives or emotionally charged adverbs.

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Newspapers

1. New York Times
2. Xalq so'zi